

Bhūtaḍāmaratantra (Buddhist)

By Aaron Michael Ullrey, University of Houston, University of Naropa

Entry tags: Tibetan Buddhism, Tantric Buddhism, Religious Group, Text, Buddhist Traditions, Magic, Tantra

A Buddhist tantra text, likely early, that is later absorbed in Hinduism with a reframed Śaiva perspective. See another entry on Bhutadamara as a Śaiva hindu source. The text was likely composed in its earliest forms its earliest form in Eastern South Asia, but it was revered and spread throughout the Himalayas and Tibet. The text opens with narrative opening in which Maheśvara (Śiva) is dominated, killed, and revived, converted by Vajradhara. After this Maheśvara is considered a protector of Buddhism. Maheśvara is also considered the lord or the supernatural hordes. And sequences of supernatural beings, mostly female are the main concern of this text. Multiple sādhanas conjure female deities that covert with yogīs, granting them incredible riches and powers. Included are Yakṣinīs, Bhūtiṅī, Nāginīs, and more. The standard ritual describes eight to twelve spirit goddesses, then specific offering, rituals, and mantras for each. If the ritual is successful, the goddesses come forward to bless the practitioner and grant wealth, magical powers, sovereignty, divine maidens. The practitioner sometimes copulates with the spirit goddesses. The source closes with a vague discussion of the different emptinesses. This buddhist text has never been edited or translated until Ullrey, Grim Grimoires, Dissertation UCSB, 2016. The Hindu version has been edited and published several times. The Buddhist version has been translated into Tibetan and included in the tantric canon.

Date Range: 700 CE - 900 CE

Region: Tibet and the Himalayas

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China

'Greater Tibet', Tibetan cultural areas of the Tibetan Plateau and the Himalayas

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Ullrey, A Michael. Grim Grimoires: Pragmatic Ritual in the Magic Tantras, PhD Dissertation, UCSB, 2016

– Source 2: Bhattacharya, Banoytosh. "The Cult of Bhutadamara." Proceeding and Transactions of the All India Oriental Research Conference, 6, 1933, pp. 349–370.

– Source 1: Davidson Ronald M. Indian Esoteric Buddhism : A Social History of the Tantric Movement. Columbia University Press 2002.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/4vt6f325>

– Source 1 Description: <https://read.84000.co/translation/toh747.html#UT22084-095-002-chapter-1>

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b10082462q/f1.item>

– Source 1 Description: <https://read.84000.co/translation/toh747.html#UT22084-095-002-chapter-1>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Printed with moveable type

Notes: There are many versions of this text. The Tibetan is found in the Tibetan derge tantric canon. The majority of Buddhist sanskrit sources are found in manuscripts in Nepal. Hindu versions are found throughout India and Nepal.

Number of sheets

– Bound

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: Wood pulp of varied age

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb
– No

↳ Cemetery
– No

↳ Temple
– Yes

Notes: The tibetan version is found in the tantric canon which resides, in printed woodblock form, in many many Tibetan Buddhist temples.

↳ Shrine
– No

↳ Altar
– No

↳ Devotional marker
– No

↳ Cenotaph
– No

↳ Church
– No

↳ Mosque
– No

↳ Synagogue
– No

↳ Triumphal Arch
– No

↳ Monument
– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Manuscript versions can be found in Tibetan literary archives, but the Sanskrit versions are found primarily in the GNMPP archives and in the royal archives in Kathmandu.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

Notes: Absolutely in the Tibetan context where the canon is recited regularly.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

Notes: The text opens with a story of its revelation. The Buddha takes the form of a wrathful Vajradhara who threatens and kills all the demons (Bhutas) including Maheshvara who is dominated and reborn to be a protector of all buddhists. This converted lord enlivens all the rituals within.

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– Yes

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: In the tibetan context there is a history of debate and interpretation, but we do not

know about the Indic context.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– I don't know

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– Yes

Notes: Male Tibetan monks.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– I don't know

Notes: Possibly only vracaryas would explicate and use this text; they are highly initiated tantra Buddhist teachers

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: The tibetan tantric canon is closed, but commentaries may still be written.

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– No

Notes: Not on this text per se, but others are.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: Ritual based tantra sanskrit, which is then translated into classical literary tibetan.

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: Indian Tantra buddhists saw this as endogenous, tibetan buddhists as exogenous

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: Indian Tantra buddhists saw this as endogenous, tibetan buddhists as exogenous

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

Notes: In its tibetan forms the sanskrit mantras are transliterated but the sanskrit directions, lore, and narratives are translated.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

Notes: Both literary tibetan and sanskrit are very specific languages known only to the elite.

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Institutions

Notes: Tibetan buddhist monastics and Indian tantra buddhist initiates

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious

language(s) for this text?

– Yes

Notes: In Tibet, the government and aristocracy also sponsored the reproduction, performance, and transmission of the tantra canon.

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– No

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There were likely Sanskrit oral traditions, but they are lost. There continues to be a Tibetan tradition of commentary.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This text could have been recited publicly, though the lore would not likely be done so. Ronald Davidson argues that these texts framed with triumphant narratives about a Buddha figure dominating a Śiva figure would have been performed or derived from performed tales. As to the lore itself, I think it was read by individuals who wanted to learn and perform these rituals to perform them and gain the relationship and power of the female spirit beings.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: Buddhists are called to spread the message. Also, the text would pull already Buddhist folk to tantra Buddhism.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

Notes: The conversion narrative suggests that the text should be used to convert.

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing or missionary work part of the historical culture of the community referenced in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Buddhism is all about spreading the word. Also, Buddhists would set up varied shrines that would have worked like missions. Buddhist monestaries in India dispensed elder care and medicine. In Tibet, the monasteries were corporations but had some missionary service perspectives.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The framing, the conversions, and the buddhist nature suggests proselytizing and conversion. That said, the lore about the spirit deities does not necessarily lend itself to proselytizing. That said, this text demonstrates buddhist having dominion over pan Indian hordes of female deities. It is unclear who first had the dominance over such creatures in the visionary manner of the texts, wither the Buddhist or the HIndus. But textually the Buddhist version of this type of tantra seems the earliest.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force?

– Yes

Notes: The frame story shows a Buddha figure killing many Śaiva figures and Maheśvara himself only to revive the figures, convert them, and make them protectors of the dharma and tantra buddhist practitioners.

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– Yes

Notes: Toward non Buddhist and toward more mainstream Buddhists to turn them into Tantra buddhists

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

Notes: The frame narrative suggest proselytization and conversion.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: The tantra buddhists, Vajracaryas, were converting mainstream Mahayana buddhists to a higher degree of initiation and practice into tantra. Arguably the power and magic might would also appeal to lay folk.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Yes

Notes: This all requires some nuance. The mantra sections of the text would be recited. And that recitation would cause the spirit beings to arrive, so if they are the audience then there would be the effect of compelling them to come. A guru would read the mantra to empower it. In the tibetan context, this text would be read to give a "reading transmission" that would empower the listener upon initiation to practice the text and work with the buddhist deity Bhutadamara. So it would unlock wisdom and power through reciting and hearing.

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

↳ On the reciter?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

Notes: As far as read and studied, the specific reading with the eyes would not necessarily have any effect.

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– No

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: Rituals involve going to a secretive and isolated place, performing varied offerings and varied mantras, this would call forth varied female spirit beings. Should they be greeted properly and the practitioner not afraid, then they would grant power and gifts, otherwise they

may kill the conjurer.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– No

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: Single practitioners would perform the rituals alone in an isolated place

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 1

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: On the desired occasions.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: The distinction between ritual practices and identity between the Hindus and Buddhists is really fluid at the time when it comes to manipulating local spirit beings. In tantra this is especially the case. In this text, likely, the Buddhists were creating rituals inspired by HIndus and borrowing pan Indian pantheons of spiritual beings to create its own type of text and practice. The HIndus later appropriate this text.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: As offerings to spirit beings, not for intoxication as an end in itself.

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Notes: A wide range of offerings and consumables are manipulated throughout the text.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Notes: This is a book of magic rituals, not a magic book. Later in the Tibetan tradition the text would have all the power of a canonical tantra, becoming a holy thing in itself.

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: The text does not contain art but there are Tangka versions of the central deity, Vajradhara, as Bhutadhamara found throughout the Himalayas.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of different sanskrit versions of this text, some Hindu and some Buddhists. The Buddhist texts appear oldest. There are varied versions of the text in Tibetan translation. The tibetan translation would be seen as authoritative, being considered a perfect translation of the sanskrit; that said there are many problems with the Tibetan translation.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: Included in the Tibetan tantra canon

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: At one point, yes, but not now.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– Yes

Notes: The degree that such texts and practices are endorsed varies.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Yes

↳ How are the volumes ordered?

– Specify: Tibetan canon is grouped by genre. And the tibetan text is part of that canon.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: Ritual list and ritual manual

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: The text would be in line with Buddhism and tantra buddhism

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: It is Buddhism, so there is no soul. But there appears to be no sense of soul operation from body in any of the rituals.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Notes: Travel through the bardo and then reincarnation

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– I don't know

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The tibetan Buddhism version of this source would be connected to notions of the Bardo and interstitial spaces between lives.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

↳ In human form?

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear and depends on what sources are examined.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?
– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?
– Yes

Notes: Rebirth connected to both karma and experiences between lives.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?
– I don't know

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?
– Yes

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions?

–Specify: Varied understanding of the means of reincarnation and the propulsion of the cit from life to life.

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

–Specify: I would argue there are tantra buddhist groups that assert an essential quality that passes between lives.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: There are practices undertaken in cremation grounds. But the burials themselves are not described.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Plenty of funerary imagery and ingredients, but no veneration of the dead or specific funeral rituals.

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: Theoretically there are ghosts called Bhutas and Bhutinis, and the term can be translated as ghosts, but these are not necessarily human.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The majority of the text is a catalog of rituals to attract, appease, and maybe manipulate supernatural beings.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– I don't know

Notes: This is hard to say. First the yogis hear things or feel wind, and then it reads like the spirit beings physically and visibly appear.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: Presence of winds. Copulation with some of them.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: These spirits all have different abilities and knowledges some restricted and some not. Some seem to have all knowledge, some just a little. Their powers and gifts range from sorta mundane to celestial. For instance, giving someone money and food vs. granting them

universal sovereignty and riding the back of the spirit being into the heavens.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– I don't know

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
– I don't know

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

Notes: If greeted properly they are generous, if improperly they are deadly.

↳ Supernatural beings can reward
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

Notes: Some of the visions may be dreams

↳ In trance possession?

– I don't know

Notes: Also these very rituals may be causing spirit possession. That is one interpretation.

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

Notes: Some creatures may tell the future, but there are no clear divination practices.

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Notes: They seem more direct, but there could be general luck from revering such deities and doing such practices.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: They can be angered. Also, the text argues in the opening that these creatures afflict human beings, but the text causes the human to thereafter be protected by those deities through the use of this text.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: Some seem very hungry, but what do they eat? They eat the offerings, they eat the sexual substances of the yogi, and sometimes they eat the yogi.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: The story at the opening is rendered as if it physically happened, but it is a mythological narrative.

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: All of the above!

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: The biggest punishments are for doing the rituals wrong which will cause the wrath of the spirit beings.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: The spirit beings if properly worshipped will grant all manner of powers, wealth, longevity, jewelry, celestial food, spirit being wives, or consort relationships with the spirit beings who grant all manner of wonderful things.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: All manner of rewards are granted by the spirit beings.

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

- ↳ Consists of success in battle?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
 - No
- ↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of success on journeys?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: This belongs to a general Buddhist and tantra Buddhist practice, but there are no general social norms prescribed in the text.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: Considering that this is a tantra, it belongs to a nonconventional ritual mode which nuances usual distinctions.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: There is little to no doctrine in this text.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: If this was practiced by monastics they would be celibate outside these practices.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: If you mean offerings as sacrifice, then there are many offerings of valuable substances depending on which spirit being is being called.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The rituals themselves are sometimes very long and some very short.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Yes

Notes: The rituals require manipulating dangerous substances but also involve taking the risk that these spirit beings may be violent and lethal if the ritual is not done correctly or the performer is deemed lacking.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Notes: It is a buddhist text, so it has ethics, but it is a tantra text that supersedes normal Mahayana ethics.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: The majority of the rituals are done by individuals based on their specific desires.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Rituals are votive.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: As a tantra, the text may be a part of larger tantra ritual cycles, but the text itself does not connect directly to these sources.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: But tantra practitioners generally would be in relationships of kin with guru and other initiates.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

Notes: The opening frame has a conflict between the Buddha and all the hostile creatures, and he kills them all and converts them, which is epic. But Maheshvara refuses to convert, so he becomes Varjadhara and emanates many vajradharas from every pour. Furthermore, after killing Maheshvara, then he sends out streams from his nose to enliven and reanimate Maheshvar and his minions. It would have been seen dramatic and likely comedic, definitely epic. All of this opens a text about dominating and controlling spirit beings.

↳ Drama?

– Yes

↳ Comedy?

– Yes

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– I don't know

Notes: The general space for the ritual would require establishing the space, but it is a temporary

space, not continually maintained.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

- A Segmentary Lineage

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

- A House Society

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

- A federation or league

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

- No

Notes: But Buddhist monasteries in general would have had some notion of welfare relief.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

- No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

- No

Notes: Somewhat associated with Buddhist monasteries.

Other forms of welfare?

- No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

- No

Notes: But Buddhist teachers would have had students that were educated in this texts. Many readers and learners could be Buddhist monks that are called to a deeper level of study and practice. That said, this world of manipulating spirits could have been transmitted to lay people. Similar practices continue among Newark in Kathmandu, mostly laypeople who are tantra initiates.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Theoretically this would be only studied by monks. However, there are indications that this text represents lay practices that are being taken up by more sophisticated buddhist authors who were monastics.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: It is not explicitly gendered, but all the adjectives and nouns for practitioners are male.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are varying opinions on the presence of women in the texts and in the audiences and readers of the texts.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: There is an understanding that this text would be taught in the context of a guru and student.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: Performing that rituals bring incredible rewards.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: Results of the text may involve sovereignty, but unlike many magic texts there are no explicit references to war and war magic.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No